

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF CARYOPHYLLENIC ACID

By M. D. OWEN

A partial synthesis of caryophyllenic acid from dimethylketene and *cyclopentadiene* is described along with a suggestion as to how the final stage in the synthesis may be carried out.

Caryophyllenic acid (I) or (II) is produced during the degradation, in stages, of β -caryophyllene and the elucidation of the structure of caryophyllenic acid would provide valuable information in establishing the structure of β -caryophyllene (Ramage and Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1208). Rydon (*Chem. Ind.*, 1938, 87, 123) on the assumption that caryophyllenic acid is 2-carboxy-3:3 dimethylcyclobutylacetic acid (I), has suggested that Ruzicka's formulæ (III) or (IV) should be replaced by (V) or (VI). However, Ramage and Simonsen (*Chem. Ind.*, 1939, 88, 447), have produced evidence which shows that Rydon's formulæ are untenable.

The writer, in collaboration with Dr. G. R. Ramage and Prof. J. L. Simonsen, was engaged on the synthesis of caryophyllenic acid from dimethylketene and *cyclopentadiene* when the outbreak of war interfered with the research and it is desired to record, in brief, the progress that was made.

The following scheme represents the series of reactions which were carried out successfully :—

It has been shown by Lewis, Ramage and Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1937, 1837) that diphenylketene condenses with *cyclopentadiene* to form the unsaturated dicyclic ketone (IX) and not (X)

(IX)

(X)

Arguing by analogy it is probable that dimethylketene will give (VII) and the latter will, on oxidation, give 2-carboxy-3:3-dimethylcyclobutanone-acetic acid. Efforts to reduce this acid to caryophyllenic acid (I) by the usual methods were not successful, the alcohol being generally formed. There were, however, indications of success when sodium amalgam was used.

Other methods of synthesis have also been tried by Owen, Ramage and Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1938, 1211) and the method described above has been extended by condensing dimethylketene with *cyclohexadiene* to produce the homologue of caryophyllenic acid. It is hoped to complete and publish this work in detail at a more favourable time.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dimethylketene was prepared from dimethylmalonic acid using the method described by Staudinger (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1925, 8, 306) and *cyclopentadiene* was distilled from a mixture of its polymers using a pear fractionating column at least one foot high. Slightly more than the theoretical amount of the freshly distilled *cyclopentadiene* was added to the dimethylketene, the latter being contained in its receiver surrounded by a freezing mixture of solid carbon dioxide and ether. In about 12 hours the mixture became colourless and the pronounced camphoraceous odour of the dicyclic ketone was noticed, the yield being nearly theoretical. The ketone was distilled slowly two or three times through an air condenser to remove most of the excess of *cyclopentadiene* and it was then purified through its semicarbazone. [The yield of the keto-acid (VIII) was much reduced when the ketone was not carefully purified before oxidation.]

The dicyclic ketone was then stirred with acetone in a three-necked flask surrounded by ice and containing a thermometer and stirrer. Finely ground potassium permanganate was added in small portions over a period of about 8 hours whilst the temperature inside was not allowed to rise above 4°. At the end of this period, the acetone was removed, water was added and sulphur dioxide bubbled through until the manganese oxide had gone into solution. The acid was thoroughly extracted with ether, the extract shaken several times with sodium carbonate solution, separated, acidified, and again thoroughly extracted with ether. The m.p. of the acid was found to be 124-25°.

The above work was carried out under the direction of Prof. J. L. Simonsen and Dr. G. R. Ramage.

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